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THE PROCESS OF DIGITALIZATION AND THE KAZAKH LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article examines the influence of digital technology on the Kazakh language. The purpose of the article is to study the development of the Kazakh language in the process of digitalization, identify linguistic phenomena arising in linguistic uses and conduct their linguistic analysis. Language units collected from state portals were taken as research materials.

Keywords: Kazakh language, digitization, digital system, new words, language features.

«This research has been/was/is funded by the Committee of Science of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP19175847)»

The development of the national language is not limited to the demand and use of the native language, it directly depends on the language policy of the state, various programs and documents that support the language, as well as various extralinguistic and economic factors. The introduction of modern IT and innovative technologies into the daily life of the population also affects the development of the state Kazakh language. This article provides for a study from the point of view of sociolinguistics on how the state program "Digital Kazakhstan", approved by the resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 827 dated December 12, 2017, influenced the development of the state language, how much the use of the state language has increased, as a result of which new words have entered the language use of citizens, including various social groups. This is due to the fact that during the implementation of this state program, any new technological digital developments will be developed and put into effect in the state and official language. The target consumer of digital products are Kazakhstanis. From this point of view, it is clear that the state program "Digital Kazakhstan" has definitely influenced the development of the state language, and the article deals with linguistic issues related to the said state language.

The initial primary information on language usage in the state language on the state e.gov.kz website and platforms was collected by the field research method, the collected materials were processed, sorted, and a linguistic analysis was made.

The object of research of the article is directly related to the state program "Digital Kazakhstan" approved by Resolution No. 827 of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan on December 12, 2017, that is, the study of state language potential that has entered the digital cyberspace within the framework of this program. The main goal of the program is to accelerate

the rate of republic's economy development and improve the quality of life of the population through the use of digital technologies in the medium term, as well as to create conditions for moving the economy of Kazakhstan to a fundamentally new development path that ensures the creation of the digital economy of the future in the long term. The program will be implemented in the period of 2018-2022 and will give an additional impetus to the technological modernization of the country's flagship industries, create conditions for large-scale and long-term growth of labor productivity. Digital Kazakhstan is a program designed to accelerate the rate of development of the Kazakh economy and improve the quality of our citizens' life [1]. That is, within the framework of the mentioned program, it can be seen that now state services, various business services have moved to digital format, and it has become much easier to get the services used in the daily life of the people. Together with these services, the state language also "started to live" in the digital system. Digital document circulation has been introduced in state bodies and organizations, quasi-state sectors, an electronic trade market has appeared, that is, the state has moved to a digital system. As a result, various language usages related to digital cyberspace appeared in the modern Kazakh language, for example: *sifrlyq memleket* (digital state), *sifrlyq qūjat ainalymy* (digital document circulation), *elektrondyq sauda* (e-commerce), *elektrondyq sauda naryǵy* (e-commerce market), *elektrondyq ūkimet* (e-government), *sifrlyq sauattylyq* (digital literacy), *«aqyldy» qala* (smart city), *«aqyldy» baǵdarşam* (smart traffic light), *«aqyldy» ūi* (smart house), *«aqyldy» esik* (smart door), *«aqyldy» saǵat* (smart clock), *onlain tōlem* (online payment), *onlain sauda jasau* (online shopping), *QR tōlem* (QR payment), etc.

During the process of globalization, various news, updates, new things, phenomena are appearing in every

sphere of society due to technology and computer equipment. All phenomena occurring in the society are reflected in the language and recorded in the language. The flow of information as a product of globalization is increasing the general priority of communication in society. Verbal and non-verbal language tools in real communication in oral form, which is carried out face-to-face, and in written form, which is carried out through handwritten text, when such communication is not formed, differ from the use of language tools in virtual, digital communication. This problem has become a special object of research among modern linguists. Because the global human race living in the information society is gradually turning to digital tools to satisfy their communication needs. The development of IT technology has opened the way for the strengthening of digital communication in society. Digital (virtual) communication space is replacing real communication day by day. Virtual communication has the potential to change the linguistic norms of real communication. Language units of virtual communication are displacing language units that have become the norm in real communication, and deviant usages are becoming “normal” for virtual communication. At the same time, as a result of the rapid development of virtual communication, new concepts, new names, new words are appearing in all languages of the world over time through the Internet and social networks [2; 144].

A brief description of the language situation in Kazakhstan. Digitization of the state in the Republic of Kazakhstan has its own peculiarities in terms of language situation: bilingualism has taken place in Kazakhstan. The peculiarity of the language situation in Kazakhstan is not only due to the development of genetically and typologically diverse languages, but also due to the simultaneous use of two large languages, Kazakh and Russian in the communicative space. “And the unique communicative space shows the limits (parameters) of the functional “well-being” of the Kazakh and Russian languages as a permanent measure of the conventional type” [3; 133]. Bilingualism is a language phenomenon that is widely studied and discussed in sociolinguistics and has its own characteristics.

Since 2006, the term “trilingualism” has been used in the territory of Kazakhstan in connection with the idea of “Trilingual language” of the then President N. Nazarbayev. “Trilingual language” policy was implemented and learning English became a priority. State bodies, quasi-state organizations will start running their websites in three languages: Kazakh, Russian, and English. In the period since 2006, individuals and social groups (“Z” generation) have appeared in the society who have mastered the Kazakh-Russian-English languages.

In the case of bilingualism or trilingualism, the form of life of the Kazakh language in the digital cyberspace is established in the digital system, because the results of the program and works related to the digitization of all Kazakhstan are reflected in the state websites. Studying the peculiarities and differences of the language in the digital system allows to determine

the state of the state language in the digital system. Regarding the linguistic situation of modern Kazakhstan, the linguistic phenomena that appeared during the digitization of the state were determined and linguistic analysis was carried out. It is assumed that the program of digitalization of the state will pave the way for the beginning of a new direction of Kazakh language education - the development of the field of cyberlinguistics. Because “Digital Kazakhstan” is a very large-scale program covering all spheres of the state, accordingly, during the implementation of the said program, new language usages and units will necessarily appear.

Digital Kazakhstan is a program designed to accelerate the rate of development of Kazakhstan's economy and improve the quality of life of our citizens. 5 main directions of the program: *Digitization of economic sectors, Transition to a digital state, Creation of an innovative ecosystem, Development of human capital, Implementation of the Digital Silk Road* (egov.kz). All the names of these routes are new usages in the Kazakh language. Here, the new linguistic usages such as “*digitization of the economy*”, “*transition to a digital state*”, “*implementation of the digital Silk Road*” are names projected according to the digital system due to the growing conflict of IT technologies. Before the state program of Kazakhstan, several state portals began to provide online services to the public.

New words that appear within the program can be grouped as follows:

1) *new usages directly imported from the English language* – «bir tereze» (*single window*), «aqyldy» datchik (*smart sensor*), «aqyldy fabrika» (*smart factory*), «aqyldy qalalar» (*smart cities*), sifirlyq kenish (*digital mine*), sifirlyq ken orny (*digital mine location*), sifirlyq basqaru (*digital management*), sifirlyq fabrika (*digital factory*), itellektualdy kölik jüesi (*intelligent transport system*), avtojoldarda jasandy intelekt engizu (*introduction of artificial intelligence on highways*), elektronдық sauda alańy (*electronic trading platform*), qağazsyz qūjat ainalymy (*paperless document circulation*), elektronдық šot-faktura (*electronic invoice*), virtualdy qoima (*virtual wareho*), elektronдық densaulıq saqtıu (*electronic healthcare*), sifirlyq biznes (*digital business*), elektronдық eńbek birjasy (*electronic labor exchange*); sifirlyq sauattylyq (*digital literacy*), sifirlyq sauattylyqty arttyru (*improving digital literacy*), bültyq esepteuler (*cloud computing*), bazalyq jāne käsibi sifirlyq dağdylar (*basic and professional digital skills*), aqparattyq qauıpsızdıq (*information security*), sifirlyq Jibek joly (*digital Silk Road*), keń jolaqty internet (*broadband Internet*); tūlgany qaşyqytqan säikestendiru (*remote identification of a person*), sifirlyq biznes (*digital business*); sifirlyq memleketke ötu (*transition to a digital state*), ekonomikany sifirlandyru (*digitization of the economy*), Sergek, etc.

2) *new usages directly imported from the English language* – E-Commerce, E-Agrotrade, Fulfillment-ortalyğy (*Fulfillment-center*), onlain jāne oflain biznes (*online and offline business*), Paper-free, e-Health, QR-kod (QR-code), Smart City, «Smart Astana», «Smart Almaty», «Smart Ontustyk», «Smart Aktobe», «Smart

Karaganda», Hub, startap-kompanialar (*start-up companies*), startap-viza (*start-up visa*), blokchein tehnologia (*blockchain technology*), hakaton (*hackathon*), 4G, 5G; Big Data, tehnogialyq park (*technology park*), vaip-şop (*wipe-shop*), baier (*buyer*), etc.

3) *hybrid words, one part of which is Kazakh, and the other part is directly from English* – startap-mädeniet (*start-up culture*), IT käsiperlik (*IT business*), tehkäsiperlik (*technical entrepreneurship*), venchurlyq qarjylarndyru (*venture financing*), venchurlyq jobalar (*venture projects*), Big Data taldu (*Big Data analysis*), kiber qaupsızdık (*cyber security*), internet-düken (*online store*), onlain tölem (*online payment*), QR tölem (*QR payment*) etc.

In the given examples, as a result of the development of digital technology, words that do not connect in the Kazakh language are combined, new concepts and names are emerging. The words “*smart*” city, “*smart*” traffic light, “*smart*” door, “*smart*” factory mean the names of tools that make everyday life easier. Before the digital era, the word “aqyldy” (smart) in the Kazakh language was used to refer to a living being with a mind and consciousness, that is, a person. Currently, this word is actively used in relation to various products of artificial intelligence. *Bültyq esepteuler* (Cloud computing) is a new word created by direct translation, a name that has become a term for IT technology. *Sifrlyq Jibek joly* (The Digital Silk Road) is a projected version of the Great Silk Road according to the modern virtual system. The Great Silk Road is a historical thoroughfare that connected the East and the West, united world civilizations, and contributed to the development of human society. *Digital Silk Road* is a historical and cultural name reproduced in a virtual system. *QR payment* is a type of online payment that simplifies people's everyday life and allows remote payment. At present, the phrases “*QR-kodpen töleu*” (pay with QR code) and “*QR-men töleimn*” (I pay with QR) are actively used.

Currently, due to the rapid development of IT technology in the world, all insurances related to meeting the social and material needs of the people are being transferred to electronic digital format. This process greatly simplified people's life and public services, digitalized the circulation of funds, and created electronic money. All the achievements of IT technology, which are widespread in the world, are realized through language. This factor indicates the high potential of the language. Studying the development of the state language, its function, potential and status between the state and the people within the framework of the digitization of Kazakhstan will help to identify new aspects and nuances of the state language that has entered the digital format. The peculiarity of the Kazakh language in the digital era is that words that were not connected before, that did not have a place in the word-formation system of the Kazakh language, are combined with each other, giving a new name and a new concept. On the one hand, this is a phenomenon necessary for language purity and language culture, on the other hand, it shows the flexibility of the Kazakh language, the potential of the Kazakh language.

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